

COVID^X

DATA vs COVID-19

THE GAME CHANGERS

OPEN
CALL
1

Results in a Nutshell

COVID-X Program targets European Start-Ups and SMEs [at TRL7] developing data and AI solutions tackling coronavirus. The call was closed in January 2021, and the selected teams joined COVID-X Acceleration Program in April 2021 for 10-months to boost their launch to the markets.

Adwarded solutions

SELECTION PROCESS

Addressed clinical challenges

The 16 COVID-X Game Changers develop technology solutions supporting healthcare services to take better and more efficient care of COVID-19 patients. Each solution focuses on a specific clinical challenge related to prognosis, diagnosis or follow-up.

16 game changer solutions

Involved countries

The funded solutions involve technology & healthcare organizations from

12
European member states
as well as one healthcare provider from India (not eligible for obtaining the direct funding)

29
organizations
joining the COVID-X Program through the OC#1

Game changing technologies

The Game Changing solutions deploy all AI & Data technologies in their fight against COVID-19. Their innovation is complemented with technologies that endorse the power of data.

Voice processing

AI & Data

Natural language processing (NLP)

Connected mobile devices

Biomarkers

Micro projectors

Edge computing

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Program

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